

Business Sustainability Strategy by Building Competitive Advantage Due to the Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic

(Qualitative Study At Mommies Baby and Kids Spa Batu City)

Yogie Firman Darajat, Ratnawati, Agus Subroto

Postgraduate Master of Management, University of Wisnuwardhana Malang

Abstract: Competition in business requires actors to be more creative and innovative in offering advantages compared to competitors. Business people are required to formulate and implement business strategies. The goal is to survive, develop the business and even to be able to compete, seize and dominate the market share. For this reason, strategy is the key to achieving competitive advantage and success in a business. Indonesia is now a mature business in the MSME field. One of the MSMEs that has recently started to appear in cities or regencies in the archipelago includes SPA salons specifically for mothers, children and babies which is no stranger to seeing these special SPA salons popping up. However, in 2020 the COVID-19 pandemic began to spread to all regions in Indonesia. Efforts to prevent its spread were carried out and campaigned. The purpose of this study is to find out how the strategy carried out by MSME actors in carrying out their business operations during the COVID-19 pandemic crisis, in an effort to maintain the continuity of their business by using their competitive advantages and creating comparative advantages. The results of this study show that the application of business strategies to MSME actors is classified as successful in the process of stabilizing the return of MSME businesses compared to MSME business actors who do not plan their business strategy. The management and development of MSME actors from the Regional Government is classified as successful.

Keywords: Strategy, Business Sustainability, Competitive Advantage, Smes

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of a problem in business is unavoidable. Business people are required to formulate and implement business strategies. The goal is to be able to survive, develop the business and even compete to seize and dominate the market share. For this reason, strategy is the key to achieving competitive advantage and the success of a business. The Micro, Small and Medium business sector is one of the important sectors in the development of the national economy. On the other hand, this business sector has also been able to contribute to driving Indonesia's economic growth so far. The strategic position of the MSME sector is also because this sector has several advantages over large businesses. The problems faced by MSMEs cause the low competitiveness faced by MSMEs (Suharto & Rokhman TNR, 2020). The advantages of this sector include the ability to absorb labor and use local resources, and the business is relatively flexible (Supriyono, 2006). One of the MSMEs that has recently started to appear in cities or regencies in the archipelago includes SPA salons specifically for mothers, children and babies which is no stranger to seeing these special SPA salons popping up. The rise of the baby SPA phenomenon has been felt since the last few years, especially among urban communities. A variety of interesting activities, both for babies and mothers, are intensively offered, thereby encouraging mothers to take their babies for SPA treatments.

This MSME is one that is in great demand by the community, especially among new households. The main objective of this effort is to improve the health of mothers and babies in several forms of treatment. Treatment for babies is to improve the baby's blood circulation, maintain the baby's fitness, eliminate baby trauma so they don't become fussy. Meanwhile, mother care aims to promote breastfeeding, strengthen uterine muscles, SPA for female parts and so on. SPA businesses for mothers and SPA for babies also receive protection from the law, one of which is.

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 8 of 2014 article 8, it states that Mom's and Baby SPA businesses are required to have a legal business registration certificate and also a comfortable service place for moms and babies. However, in 2020 the COVID-19 pandemic began to spread to all regions in Indonesia. Efforts to prevent its spread were carried out and campaigned. The Ministry of Cooperatives and

SMEs said that business people engaged in services and production were also most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. MSME entrepreneurs feel the decline in sales, lack of capital, and distribution delays causing the turnover of MSME actors to experience a sharp decline and even causing many to go out of business.

From the phenomenon of the COVID-19 pandemic, creative MSMEs can certainly advance the Indonesian economy. So there is a need for new breakthroughs in the business world in the field of health services, especially in midwifery and nursing. As we know, it is currently difficult for the nursing and midwifery sector to find work, so a change is needed from being an employee to becoming an independent business owner.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Strategy

The definition of strategy according to Pearce & Robinson (200) strategy is a plan which is a comprehensive and integrated unit that links the advantages of the company's strategy with its environment to ensure the achievement of company goals. The company must also be able to analyze and recognize the environmental conditions of the company so that the company can create more value than its competitors. Meanwhile, according to Wheelen & Hunger (2001) strategy is a comprehensive planning formulation of how the company will achieve its mission and goals, strategy will maximize competitive advantage and minimize competitive limitations. Companies must be able to use the advantages they have, in the midst of business competition that occurs. By providing better service to consumers than its competitors. By implementing a strategy, business actors can win competition in the field against similar business competitors by analyzing their environment. With a strategy, the company has strengths that can be highlighted and correct the weaknesses of the company so that excellence will be achieved.

Competitive Advantage Strategy

Competitive advantage is a strong link between excellence and company effectiveness in facing competition. According to David Hunger and Thomas Wheelen (2003) competitive advantage is a collection of strategies to determine the superiority of a company from its business competitors. Strategies include low cost (low cost) and differentiation. Furthermore, the combination of the two strategies is called the focus strategy.

2.2. Building Comparative Advantage and Competitive Advantage

According to Hunger and Wheelen (2003) Adam Smith put forward the theory of absolute advantage which states that because certain countries are able to produce certain goods more efficiently than others, they should specialize in the production of those goods where they have an advantage.

Comparative advantage is seen from the Indonesian dictionary, Badudu Zain (1994), where comparative is defined as comparative or expressing comparisons. So comparative advantage is an advantage possessed by an organization to be able to compare it with others. Several government agencies/institutions, by utilizing all the advantages they have, and they have one common goal, namely to realize the VISION and MISSION that they have created together. Therefore, it is clear that comparative advantage, how to achieve common goals with all the advantages possessed by both the organization and other organizations, while competitive advantage, how to take advantage of the advantages possessed by the organization to be able to achieve organizational goals,

Competitive advantage can be achieved through quality control. Strict control, starting from product planning, production process, until the product reaches the customer. This is done to achieve the quality expected by customers and increased quality will reduce damaged products even at a zero percent level, thereby not only increasing customer satisfaction, but also increasing sales, as well as the competitiveness of small and medium enterprises (Alghamdi & Bach, 2013; Hossain, Tasnim, Hasan, 2017; Singh, 2013). Perception of the brand is more about how consumers think abstractly about the brand. Because brand perception leads to intangible aspects of the brand. Consumers can imagine the relationship between their personal experiences directly or indirectly through communication media (Subroto Agus,

2.3. Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises or when abbreviated as UMKM are productive businesses owned by individuals or business entities that have met the criteria as micro-enterprises. MSMEs are often defined as various aspects and criteria depending on each country, and other aspects. Therefore, there is a need for further review regarding the definition and understanding so that an appropriate understanding of MSMEs can be obtained. In Indonesia there are various different definitions of MSMEs based on the interests of the institutions that provide an

understanding. The definition of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises is not always the same, depending on the concept used by the country. Regarding the understanding or definition of small businesses, it turns out that it varies greatly, in each country.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Types of research

This research uses qualitative research with a descriptive approach, besides that what needs to be observed is the behavior of an event or condition of the surrounding socio-economic environment which includes in the context of the problem being investigated, namely as economic behavior, because it becomes a contextual part of the object under study. In economics, for example; inflation behavior, market behavior, consumer behavior, manager behavior, accounting behavior, rising food prices, scarcity of fuel, festive atmosphere, and others.

3.2. Data and Information Sources

Sources of information data used in this study are subjects as informants

1. The key informant (actor) as well as the subject of the main actor who became the object of research was the owner of the Mommies Baby And Kids SPA Clinic.
2. The co-actors are Employees, Homeowners and Regular Customers.
3. Secondary data is collected through various sources that have administrative links, documents, and data that support and are needed for this research.

3.3. Data and Information Collection Techniques

Referring to the nature of qualitative research which is naturalistic inquiry, research is conducted to find phenomena according to what they are, which are found in research subjects. The findings as they are, can be obtained by observing processes and meanings. The data collected is more verbal in nature: words, intonation, sentence descriptions and reading of non-verbal data in the form of limb movements, changes in facial expressions, and other subtle signs (which usually accompany words and utterances). Verbal data that requires information and non-verbal data that requires context are both necessary because they contain all empirical facts that have a depth of meaning as the message.

Interviews were conducted in pre-arranged meetings or spontaneously. This interview was carried out either with or without an interview guide and was applied individually. The use of an interview guide (guide) in the form of a number of points related to the focus of the research is intended to keep the interviews directed, so that in-depth information is obtained.

3.4. Data analysis technique

Qualitative data analysis is the process of systematically searching for and organizing interview transcripts, field notes, and other collected materials to increase the researcher's understanding of all of these materials and to enable the researcher to report what has been found. Ratnawati et al (2020) a qualitative approach is carried out using the lecture method, tutorial method and discussion method.

IV. DISCUSSION

4.1. Description of the Research Area

Subject Discovery

Before conducting interviews at the beginning of the study, the researchers visited the Mommies Baby and Kids SPA Clinic. This visit is in the framework of the owner's willingness to conduct interviews. After visiting several times and observing Mommies Baby and Kids SPA in a field survey, the researcher decided to interview 5 (five) informants who were willing to be interviewed. The five informants were SilvianaStyowati (Clinic Business Owner), Ana Sofiana (SPA Clinic Employee), Winarsih (House Owner), and ChinzetaPuteri (SPA Clinic Customer), Dynasty (SPA Clinic Customer). The selection of qualitative research subjects is not based on representation but uses an approach based on certain criteria that are in accordance with the objectives and focus of the research. The research subject was SilvianaStyowati as actor (subject #1) and four other informants as co-actor (subject #2, subject #3, subject #4, and

subject #5.

Subject#1

Decided to create a new strategy so they could rise from the downturn they experienced. They started offering Home Visite services (services from home) where this treatment service Silvi as a therapist came to the patient's house to do the treatment. But the weakness of this method is that they can only do a few treatments except baby swimming. By using this strategy, they slowly started to make a comeback and the clinic's income began to gradually improve and stabilize.

Subject#2

The owner has to make a strategy so that the clinic's operational activities can continue even though there are many obstacles and obstacles in its business activities. "I was really sad too, at the clinic at that time no patients came, the clinic income came from wages from the daycare (childcare) that I was caring for about 3 children, at that time, so just to pay my salary, Ms. Silvi, who often hit me". Even so, the business activities continued to run like flowing like water, until finally a way was thought of so that services could still be carried out to customers who wanted treatment but were constrained so they could not come to the place, this method was finally made in such a way as a possible strategy for the Mommies clinic Baby And Kids SPA,

Subject#3

Now the business is independent, there are also many who come from out of town too, on average those who rent the villa next door also have their children on vacation at the SPA there, I was so excited that I also saw someone come angry, it turned out that the boss was there down (at the clinic that is located in the area under the city of stone). What the subjects felt was that there had been good progress, and in the future the clinic could operate properly even though it is currently being hit by a pandemic crisis but there are still many customers who come to get services there, especially if in the future nothing has happened and the economy has improved. back to normal.

Subject#4

When asked about the Mommies Baby And Kids SPA clinic, the young mother who is often called by the name of Mrs. Daughter was very enthusiastic in explaining the advantages compared to when she entrusted and entrusted her baby to her previous daycare, she was also actively promoting the clinic to neighbors and relatives. close relatives or fellow teachers at the school he teaches to try treatment services at the Mommies Baby And Kids SPA clinic as a form of appreciation for the services that have been obtained and given to their children.

When asked about the Mommies Baby And Kids SPA clinic, the young mother who is often called by the name of the Dynasty's mother was very enthusiastic in explaining her advantages compared to when she had treatment with other therapists she had visited and tried treatments elsewhere, she was also actively promoting the clinic to friends who also have babies, to try treatment services at the Mommies Baby And Kids SPA clinic as a form of appreciation for the services that have been obtained and given to their children.

V. CONCLUSION

From the advantages possessed by Mommies Baby And Kids SPA, there are several drawbacks based on research facts, these are: (1) The environment around the clinic is starting to be less maintained, the worn out signboards have not been replaced. This makes the appearance of the Mommies Baby And Kids SPA Clinic less attractive. People don't know that the building is a Mother and Baby SPA Clinic, what people know is an ordinary house. (2) lack of entertainment facilities for visitors. This condition sometimes makes visitors bored because the entertainment is limited to the playground where there are not too many toys. (3) Treatment Services, not everything on the list can be done, which makes customers sometimes have to reschedule another day.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Ahmadi, A., &Supriyono, W. 2006. Learning Psychology. Jakarta: RinekaCipta. Sunarto. 2002. Strategic Management. Malang: Panca Tunggal.
- [2.] Alghamdi, H. & Bach, C. 2013. Quality as Competitive Advantage. International Journal of Management & Information Technology, 8(1), 1265-1272.

- [3.] Badudu, JS and Zain. 1994. Indonesian General Dictionary. Jakarta: Sinar Harapan Library
- [4.] David, Hunger J. &L..Wheelen, Thomas. 2003. Strategic Management. Yogyakarta: Andi.
- [5.] Hakim, L.2020. Etika Bisnis Dalam Corporate Social Responsibility Untuk Penguatan Promosi Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan Kota Malang. Pangripta, 3(1), 447-455.
- [6.] Kuncoro, Mudrajad. 2005. Strategy How to Achieve Competitive Advantage. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [7.] Kotler, Philip & Kevin Lane Keller, 2009. Marketing Management Volume 1. Issue 12 and Edition 13 Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [8.] Moleong, Lexy J. 2016. Qualitative Research Methodology. Bandung: Rosdakarya Youth.
- [9.] Muhammad, Suwarson. 2017. Strategic Management: Concepts and Tools of Analysis, Sixth Edition. Yogyakarta: UPP STIM YKPN.
- [10.] Pearce, John A. & Richard B. Robinson. 1997. Strategic Management: Formulation, Implementation and Control. Volume 1. Jakarta: Script Binarupa.
- [11.] Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia No. 8 of 2014. Regarding registered health business licenses.
- [12.] Porter, Michael E. Competitive Strategy. 1997. Industry and Competitor Analyzing Techniques. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [13.] Grab it, Freddy. 2018. SWOT Analysis: Techniques for Dissecting Business Cases, Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama
- [14.] Ratnawati, Limgiani, Atiwi, E., Rofiq A, & Annisa. 2020. Financial Recording and Management Assistance Rifaie Toserba Cooperative (Community Assistance Program of Al-Rifa'ie Gondanglegi Foundation Malang Indonesia). International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology. 5(12).286-288.
- [15.] Subroto, A. 2021. The Effect of Consumer Attitude and Physical Environment on Buying Decisions by Brand Equity at Gramedia Book Store Matos Malang. International Journal of Business Marketing and Management (IJBMM). 6(12) 01-07.
- [16.] Suharto & Rokhman., TNR. 2021. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Intellectual Capital, Knowledge Management and Competitive Advantage of MSMEs. International Journal of Small and Medium Enterprises. 4(1). pp. 59-68
- [17.] Tyoso, JSP & Widyaningrum. 2012. Product Quality Analysis, Costs, and Sales Volume. Fiber Acitasa UNTAG Scientific Journal Semarang, 1-10.
- [18.] Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 20 of 2008. Concerning Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises.